

Imaging features of pediatric hepatic sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma.

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Abstract

Background: Sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma (SEF) is a rare variant of fibrosarcoma with less than handful of pediatric cases presented in the literature and almost all prior publications focused on pathology. There is no description of imaging features of hepatic SEF in the literature.

Case presentation: A 17-year-old female with chronic abdominal pain and pruritis was found to have a large solid mass in the right hepatic lobe on ultrasonography (US). Further imaging by contrast enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and Fluorine 18-Fluorodeoxyglucose Positron Emission ¹⁸FDG-PET were performed. Core biopsy of the hepatic mass revealed SEF. Two months later, she underwent liver transplantation. On clinical and imaging follow up to 24 months after transplantation, no evidence of recurrence or metastasis identified.

Conclusion: This paper presents the first multimodality imaging features of primary hepatic SEF in an adolescent patient.

Keywords: Pediatric imaging- oncology- Fibroepithelial sarcomas-Organ transplant.

1. Introduction

Sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma (SEF), first described by Meis-Kindblom et al. in 1995, is a rare variant of fibrosarcoma that shows round or oval epithelioid cells within a dense collagenous matrix [1]. Despite its benign histologic appearance, characterized by an absent or low mitotic rate, this tumor exhibits aggressive clinical behavior. It has a 37% likelihood of local recurrence [2] and an 80% tendency for synchronous or metachronous distant metastasis [3], making it a clinically aggressive tumor.

SEF mainly occurs in middle-aged adults, and fewer than a handful of pediatric cases have been described in the literature. The locations of SEF in the pediatric cases presented in the literature include bone [4,5], kidney [6] and liver[7]. Diagnosis is challenging due to the rarity of the disease and ultimately confirmed by pathology.

Although the immunohistochemical and molecular genetic characteristics of pediatric hepatic SEF have been explored previously[7], no studies have focused on its imaging features.

Therefore, the imaging description of SEF remains poorly defined in the literature. The aim of this paper is to review US, MRI, and ¹⁸FDG PET/CT features of this rare pediatric liver malignancy. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first description of the multimodality imaging features of pediatric liver SEF in the literature.

2. Case Report

A 17-year-old female, previously healthy, presented with abdominal pain and pruritus for several months. She noticed jaundice in her eyes for the last two weeks but denied acholic stools. These symptoms were associated with a 10-pound weight loss and fatigue. She was not on any steroids or oral contraceptive pills. Initial lab data showed a total bilirubin of 4.7 mg/dL (0.0-1.2), alkaline phosphatase of 390 unit/L (40-130), AST of 101unit/L (10-45), and ALT of 162 unit/L (7-45).

Abdominal ultrasound (figure 1) showed a large lobulated mixed echogenicity mass centered on the right hepatic lobe containing several hypoechoic components with posterior acoustic shadowing without a discernible central scar. Color Doppler showed scanty peripheral vascularity without significant internal vascularity.

The spleen was moderate to markedly enlarged with a craniocaudal dimension of approximately 19 cm. Upon further laboratory evaluation, CA 19-9 was 68.8 units/mL (NI: up to 35) with normal serum alpha-fetoprotein and beta-HCG. Abdominal MRI (figures 2 and 3) showed a large predominantly hypointense mass on both T1- and T2-weighted images with heterogeneous enhancement on delayed images.

There was no signal drop throughout the lesion on out-of-phase images to suggest fat component. No central scar was appreciated within the hepatic lesion. Mild, regular dilation of peripheral intrahepatic biliary ducts was also identified due to the mass effect on the biliary system. Splenomegaly and collateral

vessels were present. There was no tumoral invasion or thrombosis of the inferior vena cava.

Liver biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of SEF. ¹⁸F-FDG PET/CT scan for initial staging showed mild to moderate uptake throughout the hepatic mass without evidence of distant

metastatic disease (figure 4). Subsequently, two months following the initial presentation, the patient underwent an orthotopic liver transplant. On the most recent surveillance imaging, 24 months after transplantation, no findings of disease recurrence were identified, and serum CA 19-9 remained normal.

Figure 1: (A) Grayscale US shows a large hepatic mass with predominantly hypoechoic content and significant posterior acoustic shadowing (arrowheads). (B) Color Doppler US shows scanty peripheral vascularity with no significant internal vascularity

Figure 2: (A, B) Axial and coronal views of T2 weighted images (WI) show predominantly hypointense large hepatic mass. Note intrahepatic mild biliary dilation distal to the large mass (black arrows), splenomegaly, and multiple signal void collateral vessels (white arrows). In-phase (C) and out-phase (D) images do not show signal drop on out-phase image to suggest fat component. Diffusion weighted image (E) and Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (F) show peripheral and target appearing restricted diffusion (white arrows) and mild T2 shine-through centrally

Figure 3: Axial T1 WI without contrast (A) and T1 WI immediate post contrast (B) show lack of early arterial enhancement. Axial T1WI 5 minutes post contrast (C) shows foci of enhancement which become more confluent and pronounced on axial T1WI 20 minutes post contrast (D).

Figure 4: Maximum intensity projection (MIP) of FDG PET (A) shows mild to moderate uptake within the hepatic mass (blue arrows) and otherwise normal biodistribution of the tracer throughout the body with no PET findings of distant metastasis. Fused axial images of FDG PET and CT scan (B) show the most FDG avid areas of the mass. Note a focus of calcification in the mass on the non-contrast CT scan image (black arrow).

3. Discussion

Two largest studies that evaluated SEF belong to Warmke[3] et al and Ossendorf et al [2] who evaluated 51 and 89 cases, respectively, with two pediatric/adolescent patients in the former and one adolescent patient in the latter study. They did not report a notable sex predilection. The reported median tumor size at presentation was around 8 cm and it is most commonly seen in the soft tissue of lower extremity, trunk, upper extremity, and head and neck region. The primary sites of metastases are lung and bone[2,5]. Differential consideration in the presented case includes benign and malignant causes; benign lesions include hepatic adenoma and focal nodular hyperplasia [8]. There was no signal drop on out-of-phase images to suggest internal fat component. Moreover, no T1 hyperintense focus on T1 WI to indicate internal hemorrhage. Malignant differential considerations in this patient include metastasis, Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), fibrolamellar HCC, undifferentiated embryonal sarcoma, cholangiocarcinoma, and angiosarcoma.

HCC and hepatoblastoma are very unlikely the absence of underlying liver disease and considering patient's age, respectively[8]. Furthermore, progressive contrast enhancement on delayed images rather than early arterial enhancement argues against HCC. Moreover, there was no central scar to support the diagnosis of fibrolamellar HCC [8].

Undifferentiated embryonal sarcoma is another differential consideration that usually presents in the right hepatic lobe and are large at the time of presentation, similar to this case. However, this tumor is rare in patients older than 15 years old and, on imaging, lack of cystic component and T2 bright matrix do not support this diagnosis[8]. The lack of robust internal vascularity argues against angiosarcoma. Delayed progressive enhancement raises concern for cholangiocarcinoma, but in the absence of predisposing underlying diseases such as choledochal cyst, primary sclerosing cholangitis, and inflammatory bowel disease, cholangiocarcinoma is very unlikely. Moreover, cholangiocarcinoma is usually T2 hyperintense [9].

T2 hypointense appearance and progressive delayed contrast enhancement on MRI are well-known imaging features of fibrous tumors, secondary to high collagenous content of the tumor[10], both of which are present in this case. Another imaging clue suggesting the dense fibrous nature of the tumor is posterior acoustic shadowing of hypoechoic components on US, indicating a dense collagenous tumor. Xia et al described the imaging features of SEF in an adult patient with pancreatic SFE with similar findings T1/T2 hypodense pancreatic mass and progressive centripetal enhancement on delayed images [11].

Several prior case reports described T2 hypointense appearance of intracranial metastases, ethmoid sinus, and intramuscular SEF [12–15]. Tomimaru et al. presented the first adult case of SEF in a 35-year-old patient with a 7 cm right hepatic lobe mass and inferior vena cava invasion at the time of presentation with delayed centripetal enhancement on contrast enhanced CT images [16].

This finding is expected considering high fibrous content. Ding et al. described MRI findings in a 19-year-old patient with SEF of the right fibula as a T1/ T2 hypointense mass with faint peripheral contrast enhancement during arterial phase and progressive enhancement during venous phase [17]. SEF has been described as a very slow growing nature based on observation of superficial soft tissue tumors[2,18]. In the presented case, the presence of cavernous venous formation at the porta hepatis and splenomegaly support the slow growing nature of SEF.

4. Conclusion

Pediatric SEF in the liver is extremely rare with no described imaging appearance in the current literature. In this presented case, significant posterior acoustic shadowing of the hypoechoic component of the hepatic mass on ultrasonography corresponding to low signal T2 appearance, and progressive delayed enhancement on MRI are imaging clues that can help radiologists to arrive a narrow differential consideration and differentiate this tumor from other hepatic malignancies.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All relevant data for this study, either included in the manuscript or provided as supplementary material, has been anonymized and is available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author, GS.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Informed written consent was obtained from patient's guardian for the publication of this report.

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